

Green Architectural Tactics for ML-Enabled Systems

This document contains the supplemental material for the ICSE SEIS 2024 submission titled "[A Synthesis of Green Architectural Tactics for ML-Enabled Systems](#)". We provide a catalog of 30 architectural tactics to improve the environmental sustainability of ML-enabled systems.

Green Architectural Tactics for ML-Enabled Systems

Data-centric	Algorithm design	Model optimization	Model training	Deployment	Management
T1: Apply sampling techniques T2: Remove redundant data T3: Reduce number of data features T4: Use input quantization T5: Use data projection	T6: Choose an energy-efficient algorithm T7: Choose a lightweight algorithm alternative T8: Decrease model complexity T9: Consider reinforcement learning for energy efficiency T10: Use dynamic parameter adaptation T11: Use built-in library functions*	T12: Set energy consumption as a model constraint T13: Consider graph substitution T14: Enhance model sparsity T15: Consider energy-aware pruning T16: Consider transfer learning T17: Consider knowledge distillation	T18: Use quantization-aware training T19: Use checkpoints during training T20: Design for memory constraints*	T21: Consider federated learning T22: Use computation partitioning T23: Apply cloud fog network architecture T24: Use energy-efficient hardware T25: Use power capping T26: Use energy-aware scheduling T27: Minimize referencing to data*	T28: Use informed adaptation* T29: Retrain the model if needed T30: Monitor computing power

The symbol * means the tactic was found with the help of the focus group.

T1: Apply Sampling Techniques

Tags

data-processing, machine-learning, measured, energy-footprint

Categories

data-centric

Description

The size of input data has a positive correlation with the energy consumption of computing. Therefore, reducing the size of input data can have a positive impact on energy efficiency of machine learning. Reducing input data can be done by using only a subset of the original input data. This is called sampling. There are different ways of conducting sampling (e.g., simple random sampling, systematic sampling), As an example, Verdecchia et al. (2022) used stratified sampling, which means randomly selecting data points from homogeneous subgroups of the original dataset.

Participant

Data Scientist

Related Software Artifact

Data

Context

Machine Learning

Feature

Data Preprocessing

Intent

Enhance energy efficiency by utilizing a subset of input data for training and inference.

Target Quality Attribute

Energy Efficiency

Other Related Quality Attributes

Accuracy, Data Representativeness

Measured Impact

Sampling has the potential to significantly reduce energy consumption during model training. Verdecchia et al (2022) achieved decrease in energy consumption of up to 92%.

Source

Roberto Verdecchia, Luis Cruz, June Sallou, Michelle Lin, James Wickenden, and Estelle Hotellier. 2022. Data-Centric Green AI: An Exploratory Empirical Study. 35–45.

<https://doi.org/10.1109/ICT4S55073.2022.00015>

Yue Wang, Ziyu Jiang, Xiaohan Chen, Pengfei Xu, Yang Zhao, Yingyan Lin, and Zhangyang Wang. 2019. E2-Train: Training State-of-the-art CNNs with Over 80% Energy Savings. In Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems, H. Wallach, H. Larochelle, A. Beygelzimer, F. d'Alché-Buc, E. Fox, and R. Garnett (Eds.), Vol. 32. Curran Associates, Inc.

<https://proceedings.neurips.cc/paper/2019/file/663772ea088360f95bac3dc7ffb841be-Paper.pdf>

Diagram

T2: Remove Redundant Data

Tags

data-processing, machine-learning, measured

Categories

data-centric

Description

Identifying and removing redundant data for ML models reduces computing time, number of computations, energy consumption, and memory space. Redundant data refers to data points that do not contribute significantly to improving the accuracy of the model. Thus, removing these unimportant datapoints does not sacrifice much accuracy (Dhabe et al. 2021).

Participant

Data Scientist

Related Software Artifact

Data

Context

Machine Learning

Intent

Enhance energy efficiency by detecting and removing redundant data to reduce the size of input data.

Target Quality Attribute

Energy Efficiency

Other Related Quality Attributes

Accuracy, Data Representativeness

Measured Impact

Removing redundant data from the dataset leads to a smaller input data that further decreases computation, computational time, energy consumption, and memory space.

Source

Phyllis Ang, Bhuwan Dhingra, and Lisa Wu Wills. 2022. Characterizing the Efficiency vs. Accuracy Trade-off for Long-Context NLP Models. In Proceedings of NLP Power! The First Workshop on Efficient Benchmarking in NLP. Association for Computational Linguistics, Dublin, Ireland, 113–121. <https://aclanthology.org/2022.nlppower-1.12>

Priyadarshan Dhabe, Param Mirani, Rahul Chugwani, and Sadanand Gandewar. 2021. Data Set Reduction to Improve Computing Efficiency and Energy Consumption in Healthcare Domain. In Digital Literacy and Socio-Cultural Acceptance of ICT in Developing Countries. Springer, 53–64. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-61089-0_4

Diagram

T3: Reduce Number of Data Features

Tags

data-processing, machine-learning, measured

Categories

data-centric

Description

A large number of data features can lead to high computing power requirements for training and inference. Typically, machine learning scenarios involve a huge number of features or variables that describe the input data. However, not all these features are necessary for the model to make accurate predictions. Therefore, reducing these data features can lead to improved energy efficiency while still maintaining accuracy. Reducing the number of input features can be achieved by selecting only a subset of the available data features.

Participant

Data Scientist

Related Software Artifact

Data

Context

Machine Learning

Intent

Enhance energy efficiency by reducing the number of data features by choosing only a subset of all the available features.

Target Quality Attribute

Energy Efficiency

Other Related Quality Attributes

Accuracy, Data Representativeness

Measured Impact

Reducing number of input features can result in a reduction of energy consumption while still maintaining accuracy.

Source

Roberto Verdecchia, Luis Cruz, June Sallou, Michelle Lin, James Wickenden, and Estelle Hotellier. 2022. Data-Centric Green AI: An Exploratory Empirical Study. (2022). In 2022 International Conference on ICT for Sustainability (ICT4S). IEEE, 35–45. <https://doi.org/10.1002/widm.1507>

Diagram

T4: Use Input Quantization

Tags

data-processing, machine-learning

Categories

data-centric

Description

Input quantization in machine learning refers to the process of converting data to a smaller precision (e.g., reduce number of bits to represent data). For example, Abreu et al (2022) investigated different input widths (bits) and found that 10-bit precision is sufficient for achieving accuracy in models, and that increasing the number of bits does not contribute to accuracy. Therefore, using higher precision is a waste of resources. Additionally, using precise data values through input quantization can even have a positive impact on the machine learning model by reducing overfitting.

Participant

Data Scientist

Related Software Artifact

Data

Context

Machine Learning

Intent

Improve accuracy (and energy efficiency) by reducing data precision with input quantization.

Target Quality Attribute

Accuracy

Other Related Quality Attributes

Energy Efficiency

Measured Impact

<Unknown>

Source

Brunno Abreu, Mateus Grellert, and Sergio Bampi. 2022. A Framework for Designing Power-Efficient Inference Accelerators in Tree-Based Learning Applications. *Engineering Applications of Artificial Intelligence* 109 (2022), 104638. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engappai.2021.104638>

Minsu Kim, Walid Saad, Mohammad Mozaffari, and Merouane Debbah. 2021. On the Tradeoff between Energy, Precision, and Accuracy in Federated Quantized Neural Networks. In *ICC 2022 - IEEE International Conference on Communications*. 2194–2199. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICC45855.2022.9838362>

Diagram

T5: Use Data Projection

Tags

data-processing, machine-learning

Categories

data-centric

Description

Data projection means transforming data into a lower-dimensional embedding and using data to optimize projection parameters. Reducing the dimensionality of input data shrinks the dimensionality of the overall DNN, which leads to improved performance. Using data projection as a preprocessing step can result in energy improvements without sacrificing performance or accuracy.

Participant

Data Scientist

Related Software Artifact

Data

Context

Machine Learning

Intent

Improve performance (and consequently energy efficiency) by projecting data into lower-dimensional embeddings.

Target Quality Attribute

Performance

Other Related Quality Attributes

Accuracy, Energy Efficiency

Measured Impact

<Unknown>

Source

Bitva Darvish Rouhani, Azalia Mirhoseini, and Farinaz Koushanfar. 2016. DeLight: Adding Energy Dimension to Deep Neural Networks. In ISLPED '16: Proceedings of the 2016 International Symposium on Low Power Electronics and Design. Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 112–117. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2934583.2934599>

Diagram

T6: Choose an Energy-Efficient Algorithm

Tags

machine-learning, algorithms, measured

Categories

algorithm-design

Description

Different machine learning algorithms have different levels of energy consumption and computational power. For example, the K-nearest neighbor (KNN) algorithm has much lower energy consumption than the ensemble method Random Forest (RF) (Verdecchia et al., 2022). High energy consumption does not necessarily mean that those algorithms perform better or achieve higher accuracy levels than low-energy algorithms.

Participant

Data Scientist

Related Software Artifact

Algorithm

Context

Machine Learning

Feature

Inference

Intent

Improve energy efficiency by choosing an energy-efficient algorithm that can achieve wanted model outcomes.

Target Quality Attribute

Energy Efficiency

Other Related Quality Attributes

Accuracy

Measured Impact

Choosing suitable, energy-efficient algorithms that achieve wanted outcomes can reduce the energy consumption of ML models (Kaack et al., 2022).

Source

R. Verdecchia, L. Cruz, J. Sallou, M. Lin, J. Wickenden, and E. Hotellier, Data-Centric Green AI An Exploratory Empirical Study, in 2022 International Conference on ICT for Sustainability (ICT4S), Plovdiv, Bulgaria: IEEE, Jun. 2022, pp. 35–45. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICT4S55073.2022.00015>

Lynn H Kaack, Priya L Donti, Emma Strubell, George Kamiya, Felix Creutzig, and David Rolnick. 2022. Aligning Artificial Intelligence with Climate Change Mitigation. Nature Climate Change 12, 6 (2022), 518–527. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41558-022-01377-7>

Diagram

T7: Choose a Lightweight Algorithm Alternative

Tags

machine-learning, algorithms

Categories

algorithm-design

Description

Some algorithms may have lightweight alternatives. Using these lighter models can have a lower energy consumption without sacrificing other important quality attributes. For example, Sorbaro et al. (2020) noted that a Spiking Neural Network (SNN) is seen as a lightweight alternative for a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN). CNN models can be converted to SNNs without a significant loss of accuracy or performance.

Participant

Data Scientist

Related Software Artifact

Algorithm

Context

Machine Learning

Feature

Inference

Intent

Improve energy efficiency by choosing lighter alternatives of existing algorithms, if possible.

Target Quality Attribute

Energy Efficiency

Other Related Quality Attributes

Accuracy, Performance

Measured Impact

<Unknown>

Source

Martino Sorbaro, Qian Liu, Massimo Bortone, and Sadique Sheik. 2020. Optimizing the Energy Consumption of Spiking Neural Networks for Neuromorphic Applications. *Frontiers in Neuroscience* 14 (2020), 662. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnins.2020.00662>

Diagram

T8: Decrease Model Complexity

Tags

machine-learning, algorithms

Categories

algorithm-design

Description

Complex AI models have shown to have high energy consumption and therefore scaling down model complexity can contribute to environmental sustainability. Simplifying the model structure can lead to faster training and inference times, making it more efficient to deploy and use in real-world applications. For example, using simple three-layered Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) architectures (Morotti et al, 2021) and shallower Decision Trees (Abreu et al, 2020) has shown to be energy-efficient while still providing high levels of precision.

Participant

Data Scientist

Related Software Artifact

Algorithm

Context

Machine Learning

Feature

Inference

Intent

Improve energy efficiency by decreasing model complexity while still meeting accuracy requirements.

Target Quality Attribute

Energy Efficiency

Other Related Quality Attributes

<Unknown>

Measured Impact

<Unknown>

Source

Brunno A Abreu, Mateus Grellert, and Sergio Bampi. 2020. VLSI Design of Tree-Based Inference for Low-Power Learning Applications. In 2020 IEEE International Symposium on Circuits and Systems (ISCAS). IEEE, 1–5. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ISCAS45731.2020.9180704>

Elena Morotti, Davide Evangelista, and Elena Lori Piccolomini. 2021. A Green Prospective for Learned Post-Processing in Sparse-View Tomographic Reconstruction. Journal of Imaging 7, 8 (2021), 139. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jimaging7080139>

Diagram

T9: Consider Reinforcement Learning for Energy Efficiency

Tags

machine-learning, algorithms

Categories

algorithm-design

Description

Algorithms can be designed to optimize energy efficiency through reinforcement learning. Reinforcement learning receives feedback on its actions and adjusts its behavior accordingly. Reinforcement learning models can be used to identify the most energy-efficient options in real-time and make informed decisions based on this information. Additionally, other quality attributes can also be targeted for optimization.

Participant

Data Scientist

Related Software Artifact

Algorithm

Context

Machine Learning

Feature

Inference

Intent

Improve energy efficiency (or other quality attributes) by using reinforcement learning algorithms.

Target Quality Attribute

Energy Efficiency

Other Related Quality Attributes

<Unknown>

Measured Impact

<Unknown>

Source

Young Geun Kim and Carole-Jean Wu. 2020. Autoscale: Energy Efficiency Optimization for Stochastic Edge Inference Using Reinforcement Learning. In 2020 53rd Annual IEEE/ACM International Symposium on Microarchitecture (MICRO). IEEE, 1082–1096. <https://10.1109/MICRO50266.2020.00090>

Thaha Mohammed, Aiiad Albeshri, Iyad Katib, and Rashid Mehmood. 2020. UbiPriSEQ—Deep Reinforcement Learning to Manage Privacy, Security, Energy, and QoS in 5G IoT HetNets. Appl. Sci. 10, 20 (Oct. 2020), 7120. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app10207120>

Diagram

T10: Use Dynamic Parameter Adaptation

Tags

machine-learning, algorithms, energy-footprint, measured

Categories

algorithm-design

Description

Dynamic parameter adaptation means that the hyperparameters of a machine learning model are dynamically adapted based on the input data, instead of determining the exact parameters values in the algorithm. For example, García-Martín et al (2021) used an *nmin* adaptation method for very fast decision trees. The *nmin* method allows the algorithm to grow faster in those branches where there is more confidence in creating a split and delaying the split on the less confident branches. This method resulted in decreased energy consumption.

Participant

Data Scientist

Related Software Artifact

Algorithm

Context

Machine Learning

Feature

Inference

Intent

Improve energy efficiency by designing parameters that are dynamically adapted based on input data.

Target Quality Attribute

Energy Efficiency

Other Related Quality Attributes

Accuracy

Measured Impact

Using the *nmin* method in very fast decision trees resulted in lower energy consumption in 22 out of 29 of the tested datasets, with an average of 7% decrease in energy footprint. Additionally, *nmin* showed higher accuracy for 55% of the datasets, with an average difference of less than 1%.

Source

Eva García-Martín, Niklas Lavesson, Håkan Grahn, Emiliano Casalicchio, and Veselka Boeva. 2021. Energy-Aware Very Fast Decision Tree. *Int. J. Data Sci. Anal.* 11, 2 (March 2021), 105–126. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41060-021-00246-4>

Diagram

T11: Use Built-In Library Functions

Tags

machine-learning, algorithm-design, libraries

Categories

algorithm-design

Description

Apply built-in library functions in the machine learning model instead of writing custom implementations. The existing built-in library functions are usually optimized and well-tested, which is why they may have improved performance and energy efficiency compared to custom-made functions. These built-in libraries can be used for instance for tensor operations.

Participant

Data Scientist

Related Software Artifact

Machine Learning Algorithm

Context

Machine Learning

Intent

Improve energy efficiency by using built-in libraries, if possible.

Target Quality Attribute

Performance

Other Related Quality Attributes

Energy Efficiency

Measured Impact

<Unknown>

Source

Shriram Shanbhag, Sridhar Chimalakonda, Vibhu Saujanya Sharma, and Vikrant Kaulgud. 2022. Towards a Catalog of Energy Patterns in Deep Learning Development. In Proceedings of the International Conference on Evaluation and Assessment in Software Engineering 2022. 150–159.

<https://doi.org/10.1145/3530019.3530035>

Diagram

T12: Set Energy Consumption as a Model Constraint

Tags

machine-learning, model-optimization

Categories

model-optimization

Description

This tactic concerns setting a predetermined energy consumption threshold for the ML model optimization process. The optimization considers the energy consumption of the model during both the optimization and training phases. The objective is to train the model in a way that it stays within the specified energy consumption threshold. This approach views model optimization as an optimization problem, where for instance hyperparameters and the model itself are optimized based on the predetermined limits.

Participant

Data Scientist

Related Software Artifact

Machine Learning Algorithm

Context

Machine Learning

Intent

Improve energy efficiency by setting energy consumption as a constraint such that the model will stay below the threshold during both optimization and training.

Target Quality Attribute

Energy Efficiency

Other Related Quality Attributes

Accuracy, Performance

Measured Impact

<Unknown>

Source

Qu Wang, Yong Xiao, Huixiang Zhu, Zijian Sun, Yingyu Li, and Xiaohu Ge. 2021. Towards Energy-Efficient Federated Edge Intelligence for IoT Networks. In 2021 IEEE 41st International Conference on Distributed Computing Systems Workshops. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICDCSW53096.2021.00016>

Haichuan Yang, Yuhao Zhu, and Ji Liu. 2019. Energy-Constrained Compression for Deep Neural Networks Via Weighted Sparse Projection and Layer Input Masking. International Conference on Learning Representations (ICLR) (2019) (ICDCSW). 55–62. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1806.04321>

Diagram

T13: Consider Graph Substitution

Tags

machine-learning, model-optimization, measured, energy-footprint

Categories

model-optimization

Description

In the context of deep neural networks (DNN), graph substitution refers to replacing a large model with a smaller one that performs a similar task. Energy-aware graph substitution, however, means replacing energy-intensive nodes of deep neural networks with less energy-consuming nodes (Wang et al 2020).

Participant

Data Scientist

Related Software Artifact

Machine Learning Algorithm

Context

Machine Learning

Feature

Neural Networks

Intent

Improve energy efficiency by replacing energy-intensive nodes of DNNs with less energy-consuming nodes.

Target Quality Attribute

Energy Efficiency

Other Related Quality Attributes

Performance

Measured Impact

Decreased energy consumption of 24% without a significant performance loss.

Source

Yu Wang, Rong Ge, and Shuang Qiu. 2020. Energy-Aware DNN Graph Optimization. Resource-Constrained Machine Learning (ReCoML) Workshop of MLSys 2020 Conference (May 2020). arXiv:2005.05837. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2005.05837>

Diagram

T14: Enhance Model Sparsity

Tags

machine-learning, model-optimization, measured, energy-footprint

Categories

model-optimization

Description

Enhancing sparsity of a machine learning model means reducing the number of model parameters or setting their values to zero. For example, weight sparsification involves identifying and removing unnecessary or less important weights in a neural network. Enhancing model sparsity decreases the complexity of the model and consequently reduces requirements for storage and memory. Therefore, it also results in lower power consumption.

Participant

Data Scientist

Related Software Artifact

Machine Learning Algorithm

Context

Machine Learning

Intent

Improve energy efficiency by removing unnecessary or less important weights in neural networks.

Target Quality Attribute

Energy Efficiency

Other Related Quality Attributes

Accuracy

Measured Impact

Removing unnecessary or less important weights in neural networks lowers energy consumption.

Source

Xiangyu Yang, Sheng Hua, Yuanming Shi, Hao Wang, Jun Zhang, and Khaled B. Letaief. 2020. Sparse Optimization for Green Edge AI Inference. Journal of Communications and Information Networks 5, 1 (2020), 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.23919/JCIN.2020.9055106>

Diagram

T15: Consider Energy-Aware Pruning

Tags

machine-learning, model-optimization, measured, energy-footprint

Categories

model-optimization

Description

In machine learning, pruning refers to the process of reducing the complexity and size of a ML model by removing unnecessary or less important components, such as weight. In energy-aware pruning, energy consumption of a neural network is used to guide the pruning process to optimize for the best energy efficiency. With the estimated energy for each layer in a CNN model, the algorithm performs layer-by-layer pruning, starting from the layers with the highest energy consumption to the layers with the lowest energy consumption. For pruning each layer, it removes the weights that have the smallest joint impact on the output feature maps.

Participant

Data Scientist

Related Software Artifact

Machine Learning Algorithm

Context

Machine Learning

Intent

Improve energy efficiency by pruning nodes with the smallest joint impact on the output.

Target Quality Attribute

Energy Efficiency

Other Related Quality Attributes

Accuracy

Measured Impact

The energy-aware pruning method reduces energy consumption.

Source

Tien-Ju Yang, Yu-Hsin Chen, and Vivienne Sze. 2017. Designing Energy-Efficient Convolutional Neural Networks Using Energy-Aware Pruning. In Proceedings of the IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR) (pp. 5687-5695). <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1611.05128>

Diagram

T16: Consider Transfer Learning

Tags

machine-learning, model-optimization

Categories

model-optimization

Description

Transfer learning means using knowledge gained from one task (a pre-trained model) and applying it to another similar task. This is feasible only if there is an existing pre-trained model available for use. The absence of or reduction in the model training effort in case of fine-tuning results in savings in energy consumption.

Participant

Data Scientist

Related Software Artifact

Machine Learning Algorithm

Context

Machine Learning

Feature

Neural Networks

Intent

Improve energy efficiency by using transfer learning with pre-trained models whenever feasible.

Target Quality Attribute

Energy Efficiency

Other Related Quality Attributes

<Unknown>

Measured Impact

<Unknown>

Source

Nitthilan Kanappan Jayakodi, Syrine Belakaria, Aryan Deshwal, and Janardhan Rao Doppa. 2020. Design and Optimization of Energy-Accuracy Tradeoff Networks For Mobile Platforms Via Pretrained Deep Models. ACM Transactions on Embedded Computing Systems (TECS) 19, 1 (2020), 1–24.

<https://doi.org/10.1145/3366636>

Shriram Shanbhag, Sridhar Chimalakonda, Vibhu Saujanya Sharma, and Vikrant Kaulgud. 2022. Towards a Catalog of Energy Patterns in Deep Learning Development. In Proceedings of the International Conference on Evaluation and Assessment in Software Engineering 2022. 150–159.

<https://doi.org/10.1145/3530019.3530035>

Diagram

T17: Consider Knowledge Distillation

Tags

machine-learning, model-optimization

Categories

model-optimization

Description

Knowledge distillation is a technique where a large, complex model (teacher) is used to train a smaller, simpler model (student). The goal is to transfer the learned information from the teacher model to the student model, allowing the student model to achieve comparable performance while requiring fewer computational resources. Knowledge distillation improves performance when evaluating top 5 accuracy and energy consumption.

Participant

Data Scientist

Related Software Artifact

Machine Learning Algorithm

Context

Machine Learning

Feature

Knowledge Distillation

Intent

Improve energy efficiency by apply knowledge distillation of pre-trained models if they are too big for a given task.

Target Quality Attribute

Performance

Other Related Quality Attributes

Accuracy, Energy Efficiency

Measured Impact

<Unknown>

Source

Shriram Shanbhag, Sridhar Chimalakonda, Vibhu Saujanya Sharma, and Vikrant Kaulgud. 2022. Towards a Catalog of Energy Patterns in Deep Learning Development. In Proceedings of the International Conference on Evaluation and Assessment in Software Engineering 2022. 150–159.

<https://doi.org/10.1145/3530019.3530035>

Haichuan Yang, Yuhao Zhu, and Ji Liu. 2019. Energy-Constrained Compression for Deep Neural Networks Via Weighted Sparse Projection and Layer Input Masking. International Conference on Learning Representations (ICLR) (2019) (ICDCSW). 55–62. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1806.04321>

Diagram

T18: Use Quantization-Aware Training

Tags

machine-learning, model-training

Categories

model-training

Description

Quantization-aware training is a technique used to train neural networks to convert data types to lower precision. The idea is to use fixed-point or integer representations instead of the more commonly used higher-precision floating-point representations. This improves the performance and energy efficiency of the model in federated learning.

Participant

Data Scientist

Related Software Artifact

Model

Context

Machine Learning

Feature

Model Training

Intent

Improve energy efficiency by using quantization-aware training to convert high-precision data types to lower precision.

Target Quality Attribute

Accuracy

Other Related Quality Attributes

Energy Efficiency

Measured Impact

<Unknown>

Source

Minsu Kim, Walid Saad, Mohammad Mozaffari, and Merouane Debbah. 2021. On the Tradeoff between Energy, Precision, and Accuracy in Federated Quantized Neural Networks. In ICC 2022 - IEEE International Conference on Communications. 2194–2199.

<https://doi.org/10.1109/ICC45855.2022.9838362>

Martino Sorbaro, Qian Liu, Massimo Bortone, and Sadique Sheik. 2020. Optimizing the Energy Consumption of Spiking Neural Networks for Neuromorphic Applications. Frontiers in Neuroscience 14 (2020), 662. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnins.2020.00662>

Diagram

T19: Use Checkpoints During Training

Tags

machine-learning, model-training

Categories

model-training

Description

Training is an energy-intensive stage of the machine learning life cycle, which may take long periods of time. Sometimes a failure or hardware error can terminate the training process before it is completed. In those cases, the training process must be started from the beginning. The use of checkpoints however can save the trained model in regular intervals and in case of a premature termination, the training process can continue at the last checkpoint (Shanbhag et al., 2022). Using checkpoints during training improves the robustness of a ML system.

Participant

Data Scientist

Related Software Artifact

Memory

Context

Machine Learning

Intent

Improve energy efficiency by using checkpoints during training to prevent knowledge loss due to a premature termination, which would in turn require to restart the process from the beginning, therefore increasing energy consumption.

Target Quality Attribute

Recoverability

Other Related Quality Attributes

Energy Efficiency

Measured Impact

<Unknown>

Source

Shriram Shanbhag, Sridhar Chimalakonda, Vibhu Saujanya Sharma, and Vikrant Kaulgud. 2022. Towards a Catalog of Energy Patterns in Deep Learning Development. In Proceedings of the International Conference on Evaluation and Assessment in Software Engineering 2022. 150–159.

<https://doi.org/10.1145/3530019.3530035>

Diagram

T20: Design for Memory Constraints

Tags

machine-learning, model-training

Categories

model-training

Description

Model training requires memory, and sometimes memory leaks and OOM (out of memory) errors may occur during that process. If that happens, the knowledge gained during the prior training process is lost. By considering memory availability constraints and addressing possible OOM exceptions, the system can be designed to operate within the available memory limits. It reduces the likelihood of errors and prevents unnecessary energy consumption (Shanbhag et al 2022).

Participant

Data Scientist

Related Software Artifact

Memory

Context

Machine Learning

Intent

Improve energy efficiency by considering memory constraints during training to prevent knowledge loss due to a premature termination, which would in turn require to restart the process from the beginning, therefore increasing energy consumption.

Target Quality Attribute

Recoverability

Other Related Quality Attributes

Energy Efficiency

Measured Impact

<Unknown>

Source

Shriram Shanbhag, Sridhar Chimalakonda, Vibhu Saujanya Sharma, and Vikrant Kaulgud. 2022. Towards a Catalog of Energy Patterns in Deep Learning Development. In Proceedings of the International Conference on Evaluation and Assessment in Software Engineering 2022. 150–159.

<https://doi.org/10.1145/3530019.3530035>

Diagram

T21: Consider Federated Learning

Tags

machine-learning, deployment

Categories

deployment

Description

Federated learning (FL) is a machine learning approach that aims to train a shared ML model on decentralized devices. Instead of sending raw data to a central server, FL trains the model directly on the devices where the data is generated, such as mobile phones or edge devices. Only the trained data or updated model parameters are then sent to a central server. Federated learning decreases the resources needed for transferring large amounts of data to a central server, which results in improved energy efficiency.

Participant

Software Designer

Related Software Artifact

Decentralized Device

Context

Machine Learning

Feature

Model Training

Intent

Improve energy efficiency by applying federated learning to minimize data transfers, if applicable.

Target Quality Attribute

Energy Efficiency

Other Related Quality Attributes

Accuracy

Measured Impact

<Unknown>

Source

Minsu Kim, Walid Saad, Mohammad Mozaffari, and Merouane Debbah. 2021. On the Tradeoff between Energy, Precision, and Accuracy in Federated Quantized Neural Networks. In ICC 2022 - IEEE International Conference on Communications. 2194–2199.

<https://doi.org/10.1109/ICC45855.2022.9838362>

Diagram

T22: Use Computation Partitioning

Tags

machine-learning, deployment, energy-footprint, measured

Categories

deployment

Description

Computation partitioning is the process of dividing the computations of a convolutional neural network (CNN) between a mobile client and a cloud server. The goal is to optimize energy consumption and efficiency. The NeuPart framework (Manasi et al 2023) is an example of a partitioning approach. NeuPart divides computational tasks between the mobile device (client) and the remote server or data center (cloud) in real time based on energy consumption. By offloading computationally intensive tasks to the cloud and executing lighter tasks locally, NeuPart resulted in significant energy savings of up to 52% in cloud-based computations.

Participant

Software Designer

Related Software Artifact

Neural Networks

Context

Cloud

Intent

Improve energy efficiency dividing computational tasks between the mobile device (client) and the remote server or data center (cloud) in real-time based on specific conditions or requirements.

Target Quality Attribute

Energy Efficiency

Other Related Quality Attributes

<Unknown>

Measured Impact

Manasi et al demonstrated that at a certain effective bit rate and transmission power, the optimal partition for specific CNN models resulted in energy savings of up to 52.4% over a fully cloud-based computation and 27.3% over a fully in situ computation.

Source

Susmita Dey Manasi, Farhana Sharmin Snigdha, and Sachin S Sapatnekar. 2020. Neupart: Using Analytical Models to Drive Energy-Efficient Partitioning of CNN Computations on Cloud-Connected Mobile Clients. IEEE Transactions on Very Large-Scale Integration (VLSI) Systems 28, 8 (2020), 1844–1857. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TVLSI.2020.2995135>

Diagram

T23: Apply Cloud Fog Network Architecture

Tags

machine-learning, deployment, energy-footprint, measured

Categories

deployment

Description

Devices at the edge are usually connected to distant cloud services. However, bringing the cloud closer to edge devices could be more energy efficient. A cloud fog network (CFN) is one way to achieve that. CFN supports an architecture where deep neural network models are processed in servers between end-devices and clouds. For example, Yosuf et al. (2021) present a CFN architecture that consists of four layers: IoT end devices, Access Fog (AF), Metro Fog (MF), and Cloud Datacenter (CDC). This architecture led to a 68% reduction in power consumption when compared to a traditional cloud data center architecture on average.

Participant

Software Designer

Related Software Artifact

Machine Learning Algorithm

Context

Network

Intent

Improve energy efficiency by using CFNs to bring the cloud closer to edge devices and reduce energy consumption due to data transfers.

Target Quality Attribute

Energy Efficiency

Other Related Quality Attributes

Performance

Measured Impact

Yosuf et al demonstrated that on average, the use of a Cloud Fog Network (CFN) architecture led to a 68% reduction in power consumption when compared to a traditional cloud data center architecture.

Source

Barzan A Yosuf, Sanaa H Mohamed, Mohammed M Alenazi, Taisir EH El-Gorashi, and Jaafar MH Elmirghani. 2021. Energy-Efficient AI over a Virtualized Cloud Fog Network. In Proceedings of the Twelfth ACM International Conference on Future Energy Systems. 328–334.

<https://doi.org/10.1145/3447555.3465378>

Diagram

T24: Use Energy-Efficient Hardware

Tags

machine-learning, deployment, hardware

Categories

deployment

Description

The emissions of machine learning are related to used hardware. This is why using energy-efficient hardware to run machine models can reduce the power consumption of models. Energy-efficient hardware can include low-energy components. For example, the Tensor Processing Units (TPUs) developed by Google are seen as an energy-efficient alternative to CPUs and GPUs.

Participant

Software Designer

Related Software Artifact

Hardware

Context

Machine Learning

Intent

Improve energy efficiency by using energy-efficient hardware.

Target Quality Attribute

Energy Efficiency

Other Related Quality Attributes

<Unknown>

Measured Impact

<Unknown>

Source

Lynn H Kaack, Priya L Donti, Emma Strubell, George Kamiya, Felix Creutzig, and David Rolnick. 2022. Aligning Artificial Intelligence with Climate Change Mitigation. Nature Climate Change 12, 6 (2022), 518–527. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41558-022-01377-7>

Diagram

T25: Use Power Capping

Tags

machine-learning, deployment, hardware, energy-footprint, measured

Categories

deployment

Description

Power capping is a technique used to limit the amount of power consumed by a device or system, such as a CPU, GPU, or server. It involves setting a maximum power consumption threshold for the device, and dynamically adjusting the power usage to ensure that it stays below that threshold. This is typically done to manage the power consumption and heat dissipation of a device, and to prevent it from exceeding the power budget of a data center or other power-limited environment.

Participant

Software Designer

Related Software Artifact

Hardware

Context

Machine Learning

Intent

Improve energy efficiency by using power capping to limit the energy usage of a ML model.

Target Quality Attribute

Energy Efficiency

Other Related Quality Attributes

Performance

Measured Impact

Krzywaniak et al show that restricting the use of GPU resources can lead to reduced performance and longer execution times, but in certain configurations, it can also result in a significant reduction in energy consumption (up to 33%) with a moderate impact on performance.

Source

Adam Krzywaniak, Pawel Czarnul, and Jerzy Proficz. 2022. GPU Power Capping for Energy-Performance Trade-Offs in Training of Deep Convolutional Neural Networks for Image Recognition. In International Conference on Computational Science. Springer, 667–681. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-08751-6_48

Diagram

T26: Use Energy-Aware Scheduling

Tags

machine-learning, deployment, energy-footprint, measured

Categories

deployment

Description

Energy-aware scheduling refers to a strategy that optimizes the scheduling of machine learning tasks. It dynamically schedules tasks or processes based on the current energy requirements and system conditions. The objective of an energy-aware dynamic scheduling policy is to make efficient use of available computational resources.

Participant

Software Designer

Related Software Artifact

<Unknown>

Context

Machine Learning

Intent

Improve energy efficiency by dynamically managing workers to maximize the overall utilization in distributed systems.

Target Quality Attribute

Resource Utilization

Other Related Quality Attributes

Performance, Energy Efficiency

Measured Impact

Sun et al. show that energy-aware scheduling can achieve close-to-optimal resource utilization without violating the energy budget.

Source

Yuxuan Sun, Sheng Zhou, and Deniz Gündüz. 2020. Energy-Aware Analog Aggregation for Federated Learning with Redundant Data. In ICC 2020-2020 IEEE International Conference on Communications (ICC). IEEE, 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICC40277.2020.9148853>

Diagram

T27: Minimize Referencing to Data

Tags

machine-learning, deployment

Categories

deployment

Description

Machine learning models require reading and writing enormous amounts of data in the ML workflow. Reading data means retrieving information from storage, while writing data means storing or updating the information. These operations may increase unnecessary data movements and memory usage, which influence the energy consumption of computing. To avoid non-essential referencing of data, reading and writing operations must be designed carefully.

Participant

Software Designer

Related Software Artifact

ML Model

Context

Machine Learning, General

Feature

Inference

Intent

Improve energy efficiency by avoiding unnecessary data read/write operations.

Target Quality Attribute

Energy Efficiency

Other Related Quality Attributes

Resource Utilization

Measured Impact

<Unknown>

Source

Shriram Shanbhag, Sridhar Chimalakonda, Vibhu Saujanya Sharma, and Vikrant Kaulgud. 2022. Towards a Catalog of Energy Patterns in Deep Learning Development. In Proceedings of the International Conference on Evaluation and Assessment in Software Engineering 2022. 150–159.

<https://doi.org/10.1145/3530019.3530035>

Diagram

T28: Use Informed Adaptation

Tags

machine-learning, management

Categories

management

Description

Machine learning models may experience drifts that affect their functionality. In these cases, the models must adapt to the drift. Informed adaptation refers to a method of adapting the ML model only when drift is detected. Therefore, the frequency of adaptation is smaller than in blind, periodic adaptation. Informed adaptation reduces unnecessary adaptations, which consequently saves energy.

Participant

Data Scientist

Related Software Artifact

Machine Learning Model

Context

Machine Learning

Intent

Improve energy efficiency by adapting ML models based on informed drift detection.

Target Quality Attribute

Energy Efficiency

Other Related Quality Attributes

<Unknown>

Measured Impact

<Unknown>

Source

Lorena Poenaru-Olaru, June Sallou, Luis Cruz, Jan S. Rellermeier, and Arie van Deursen. 2023. Retrain AI Systems Responsibly! Use Sustainable Concept Drift Adaptation Techniques. In 2023 IEEE/ACM 7th International Workshop on Green and Sustainable Software (GREENS). 17–18.

<https://doi.org/10.1109/GREENS59328.2023.00009>

Diagram

T29: Retrain the Model if Needed

Tags

machine-learning, management

Categories

management

Description

Retraining a model refers to the process of updating or modifying an existing machine learning model. In the long term, concept drift may affect the accuracy of existing machine learning models. Retraining the model by for example training it again with new data is better than building it again in terms of sustainability.

Participant

Data Scientist

Related Software Artifact

Machine Learning Model

Context

Machine Learning

Intent

Improve energy efficiency by retraining the existing machine learning model instead of building a new one when drift is detected.

Target Quality Attribute

Accuracy

Other Related Quality Attributes

Energy Efficiency

Measured Impact

<Unknown>

Source

Lorena Poenaru-Olaru, June Sallou, Luis Cruz, Jan S. Rellermeier, and Arie van Deursen. 2023. Retrain AI Systems Responsibly! Use Sustainable Concept Drift Adaptation Techniques. In 2023 IEEE/ACM 7th International Workshop on Green and Sustainable Software (GREENS). 17–18.

<https://doi.org/10.1109/GREENS59328.2023.00009>

Diagram

T30: Monitor Computing Power

Tags

machine-learning, management

Categories

management

Description

Estimating and calculating the energy footprint of a machine learning model can help to reduce the computational power of ML models. Monitoring the energy consumption of a ML model in the long term helps to identify those components where energy is being inefficiently utilized. This can serve as a starting point for making improvements to reduce energy consumption. There has been a lack of easy-to-use tools to do that, but recently researchers have provided frameworks for how to estimate or calculate the energy footprint of machine learning.

Participant

Data Scientist

Related Software Artifact

Machine Learning Model

Context

General

Intent

Improve energy efficiency by monitoring computing power of machine learning models in the long term.

Target Quality Attribute

Energy Efficiency

Other Related Quality Attributes

<Unknown>

Measured Impact

<Unknown>

Source

Qingqing Cao, Yash Kumar Lal, Harsh Trivedi, Aruna Balasubramanian, and Niranjan Balasubramanian. 2021. IrEne: Interpretable Energy Prediction for Transformers. Proceedings of the 59th Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics and the 11th International Joint Conference on Natural Language Processing (Volume 1: Long Papers) (2021). <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2106.01199>

Mohit Kumar, Xingzhou Zhang, Liangkai Liu, Yifan Wang, and Weisong Shi. 2020. Energy-Efficient Machine Learning on the Edges. In 2020 IEEE International Parallel and Distributed Processing Symposium Workshops (IPDPSW). 912–921. <https://doi.org/10.1109/IPDPSW50202.2020.00153>

Diagram

